

INSERVICE TEACHERS' TPACK DEVELOPMENT

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Since its introduction by Koehler and Mishra (2008), various strategies have been developed to help experienced teachers build their TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge). Even in its early stages—when it was still referred to as TPCCK—researchers suggested specific methods for its development. These included collaborative learning-by-design models for in-service teachers (Koehler & Mishra, 2005) and university faculty (Koehler et al., 2004), as well as instructional systems design (Angeli & Valanides, 2005) and reflective practice (Niess, 2005) for pre-service teachers. Over time, a total of twelve distinct strategies have emerged to foster this specialized form of applied knowledge. This chapter outlines these twelve approaches and situates them within the broader context of teacher professional development (PD), highlighting recent trends in TPACK-focused teacher learning and future research directions.

Research on teacher learning suggests that the most effective PD is active, reflective, ongoing, embedded in daily practice, well-structured, and closely tied to student learning and curriculum. Collaborative and community-based PD models have been especially prominent over the past two decades (Darling-Hammond & Richardson, 2009), alongside other effective formats like coaching, mentoring, and teacher-led inquiry (Joyce & Calhoun, 2010). However, the research remains inconclusive. A wide range of factors—including individual, organizational, and contextual influences—affect the outcomes of professional learning, making it difficult to directly link specific PD characteristics to improved student outcomes across all settings (Opher & Peddler, 2011). Therefore, the effectiveness of any given PD approach often depends on how well it fits the unique needs, preferences, and contexts of individual teachers (Pea & Wojnowski, 2014). In light of this complexity, it is important to consider a broad spectrum of PD approaches in order to create more personalized and effective learning experiences for teachers.

While few scholars have attempted to systematically organize all existing PD models, Joyce and Calhoun (2010) identified five key categories: PD aimed at individual teacher growth; PD delivered by mentors or leaders; community-

based PD grounded in active learning; school or district-wide instructional initiatives; and short, workshop-based learning sessions. In contrast, Kennedy (2005) categorized nine PD models based on their underlying purposes. These include training, certification, remediation (deficit-focused), cascade training (peer-to-peer), standards-based PD, coaching and mentoring, communities of practice, action research, and transformative PD. Transformative PD, in particular, aims to foster both individual learning and broader school or systemic change.

Another framework by Rogers Park et al. (2010) classifies PD in science education by orientation, identifying five types: activity-driven, content-focused, pedagogy-driven, curriculum-based, and needs-responsive. While these frameworks help identify overall goals and structures, it is also essential to explore the specific processes that make up each model—especially when aiming to support TPACK development. To better understand these processes, the researchers reviewed 23 issues of the **TPACK Newsletter** (from January 2009 to May 2015), as well as a database of TPACK publications from before the newsletter's launch. The newsletter, distributed to about 1,200 subscribers, compiles abstracts and citations from books, articles, dissertations, and conference papers related to TPACK.

In total, 179 publications were identified that addressed the development of in-service teachers' TPACK. Of these, 63 provided sufficient detail to identify the instructional strategies and design elements used in their PD programs. From this group, 35 publications were chosen to exemplify distinct professional development models, based on the clarity and depth of the information they provided. These models are summarized in Table 1 and organized by general PD type and specific strategy for developing TPACK. Each model is explained in more detail in the sections that follow.

As the analysis of extant TPACK PD literature described above demonstrates, many approaches to TPACK development have been created and explored in the decade since the construct was named and defined. Koehler, Mishra & Cain (2013) and Koehler, Mishra, Kereluik, Shin, & Graham (2014) classify these approaches in terms of teacher knowledge-building origins and sequences. According to these authors, “PCK to TPACK” approaches help teachers to build upon existing pedagogical content knowledge to develop technological pedagogical content knowledge. “TPK to TPACK” approaches suggest that teachers begin instead with existing technological knowledge, learning to analyze and apply particular technologies in educational

environments, then use that technological pedagogical knowledge to teach specific content that is well-enhanced with use of digital tools and resources. Simultaneous PCK and TPACK development approaches encourage teachers to work collaboratively in design-based ways on problems of practice with colleagues with differing sets of expertise, developing all of the aspects of TPACK interactively and emergently (Koehler, et al., 2013, p. 18). This three-category way of conceptualizing TPACK development approaches is helpful in understanding the nature of the technology integration knowledge that teachers build when participating in these three general types of professional learning experiences. To examine the particular strategies that can be used to help teacher-learners to develop their TPACK, however, a more fine-grained classification system is needed. Focusing upon the different processes for 5 professional learning that have been used to assist teachers' TPACK growth, in addition to the sequences of the different types of knowledge developed (Koehler, et al., 2013), and the overarching structures (Joyce & Calhoun, 2010), purposes (Kennedy, 2005) and orientations (Rogers Park, 2010) to PD design can help researchers and teacher educators to build more comprehensive and pragmatic knowledge about approaches to and specific methods for TPACK development.

Given the rapid emergence of digital technologies within the first ten years of the TPCK/TPACK construct's influence upon educational research and practice, it seems probable that for at least 19 the next ten years of TPACK development, inservice teachers will continue to require – and benefit from – focused, situated, authentic, and personalized ways to develop their technological pedagogical content knowledge. By purposefully choosing among and combining the strategies and approaches classified and presented here, perhaps the design and crafting of specific TPACK development efforts can become even better matched to particular teachers' professional learning needs and preferences, and the contextual realities of their workplaces.

References

1. Allan, W. C., Erickson, J. L., Brookhouse, P., & Johnson, J. L. (2010). Teacher professional development through a collaborative curriculum project – An example of TPACK in Maine. *TechTrends*, 54(6), 36-43. doi: 10.1007/s11528-010-0452-x
2. Angeli, C., & Valanides, N. (2009). Epistemological and methodological issues for the conceptualization, development, and assessment of ICT-TPCK: Advances

in technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK). *Computers & Education*, 52(1), 154-168.

3. Angeli, C., & Valanides, N. (2005). Pre-service teachers as ICT designers: An instructional design model based on an expanded view of pedagogical content knowledge. *Journal of Computer-Assisted Learning*, 21 (4), 292–302.

4. Archambault, L. M., & Barnett, J. H. (2010). Revisiting technological pedagogical content

5. Boschman, F., McKenney, S., & Voogt, J. (2015). Exploring teachers' use of TPACK in design talk: The collaborative design of technology-rich early literacy activities. *Computers & Education*, 82, 250–262. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2014.11.010

6. Cox, S., & Graham, C. R. (2009). Diagramming TPACK in practice: Using an elaborated model of the TPACK framework to analyze and depict teacher knowledge. *TechTrends: Linking Research & Practice to Improve Learning*, 53(5), 60-69.

7. Harris, J., & Hofer, M. (2006, July). Planned improvisations: Technology-supported learning activity design in social studies. Session presented at the National Educational 22 Computing Conference, San Diego, CA. Retrieved from

8. Kennedy, A. (2005) Models of continuing professional development: A framework for analysis. *Journal of In-Service Education*, 31(2), 235-250.

9. Koehler, M. J., & Mishra, P. (2008). Introducing TPACK. In AACTE Committee on Innovation & Technology (Eds.). *Handbook of technological pedagogical content knowledge for educators* (pp. 3-29). New York, NY: Routledge.

10. Roblyer, M. D., & Doering, A. (2013). *Integrating educational technology into teaching* (6th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon

